

e-ISSN: 3048-5916

Volume 04 Issue 01
Jan - Jun 2026

Submission Date: Jan 15,
2026

Copyright Date : Feb 25,
2026

Effectiveness of Maternal Enlightenment Program Regarding Prevention and Management of Diaper Related Problems on Knowledge and Reported Practice Among Mothers of Children Aged Less Than 3 Years

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ABSTRACT

Diaper rash is a common problem which affects up to 50% of infants at some point causing discomfort and pain. The study was intended to assess the effectiveness of a Maternal enlightenment program regarding prevention and management of diaper related problems on knowledge and reported practice among mothers. The objectives of the study were to evaluate the effectiveness of Maternal enlightenment program on knowledge and reported practice regarding diaper related problems among mothers and to find out the association of knowledge and reported regarding prevention and management of diaper related problems with selected sociodemographic variables. The study was conducted using quantitative approach. A pre-experimental study was chosen; one group pretest post test was used for this study. Convenience sampling technique was used for this study. Sample size of 40 mothers of children aged less than 3 years attending the pediatric outpatient department and immunization clinic of PRS Hospital, Trivandrum are selected. Sociodemographic data sheet, a structured questionnaire to assess the knowledge and a checklist to assess the reported practice were used. It was found that 55% of mothers had moderate knowledge, 40% had poor knowledge and 5% had good knowledge. The mean knowledge score was 10.47 with a standard deviation of 2.27. Regarding reported practice, 62.5% of mothers had fair practice, 30% had poor practices and 7.5% had good practices. The mean practice score was 38.4 with

a standard deviation of 2.65. After Maternal enlightenment program post test was conducted. And it revealed that 72.5% of mothers had adequate knowledge and 82.5% of mothers had good practice regarding prevention and management of diaper related problems. The mean knowledge score increased from 10.47 in the pre test to 17.12 in the post test. The mean practice score increased

from 38.4 to 45.82 after intervention. There was significant association of knowledge and reported practice of mothers with age of child, feeding status, weaning started age, age of mothers, education status of mother, education status of father and number of diapers used. Paired 't' test showed that there was a significant improvement between pre test and post test knowledge with 't' value of 17.50 at $p < 0.0001$ and in practice with 't' value of 15.86 at $p < 0.0001$. The study concluded that the Maternal enlightenment program was effective in improving the knowledge and reported practice of mothers regarding prevention and management of diaper related problems.

Keywords: Diaper rash, effectiveness, maternal enlightenment program, health knowledge and reported practice

INTRODUCTION

Children are the most valuable resources to society. From conception to birth and beyond, careful attention and proactive care are essential to ensure optimal health and well-being. Mothers are naturally vigilant about their baby's health, and even slight changes in physical appearance, such as skin color or texture, can cause concern.[1,3]

Dermatological problems are quite common among children and about 32% of pediatric outpatient department attendance relies on these conditions. The skin of newborn and infants predisposes the development of diaper dermatitis.

A diaper is an absorbent material commonly used on newborn and infants who are incontinent and unable to reach toilet when needed. Commonly diapers are used in children until they are potty trained. At present, the demand for commercial diapers has increased due to their advanced technology and comfort realized by mothers. Disposable diapers are convenient for many parents. It is sensitive because of its warmth, moistness and strong breeding space for bacteria. Rashes and redness may be observed on the skin

of these regions, most likely to be diagnosed among infants between 8 to 12 months old. A common health problem forms continuous use of diaper above one third of infants of both genders, such as urinary tract infection due to stagnation of urine in it.[4-8]

In India, diaper rashes are commonly found during infancy. Prevalence has been reported from 4-35% in the first 2 years of life. Incidence triples in newborn and infants with diarrhea. Disposable diapers are not environmentally friendly, but are convenient to use, easily available and the need to worry about leakage is very minimum.[9,10]

The diaper needs to be changed every hour for the newborn and every 3-4 hours for an infant and toddlers. This mainly helps in preventing diaper rashes. The cause of diaper rash includes fungal, bacterial, viral and yeast infection, prolonged exposure to stool and urine, exposure to irritant brands, poor diaper techniques, soft skin, strong detergent used by the carers to wash diaper, digestive disturbance for the infant. The symptoms are red rashes with different degrees looking almost scalded to the skin around the genitals and buttocks of the

infant. Diaper dermatitis affects newborn and infants on diapers without any gender preference.[11-14]

The age range of 9 to 12 months is when the incidence peaks. About 25% of visits to primary care physicians during the first year of life are linked to dermatological symptoms, and diaper dermatitis affects approximately 50% of infants.

STATEMENT OF PROBLEM

Effectiveness of Maternal enlightenment program regarding prevention and management of diaper related problems on knowledge and reported practice among mothers of children aged less than 3 years attending the pediatric outpatient department and immunization clinic of PRS Hospital, Trivandrum.[15-18]

OBJECTIVES

- To assess the impact of a maternal enlightenment program on mothers' reported practices and awareness of diaper-related issues.
- To determine the relationship between sociodemographic factors and pretest knowledge and reported practice on the management and prevention of diaper-related issues.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The research design adopted for the present study was quasi experimental one group pre-test post-test design. The study was conducted in pediatric outpatient department and immunization clinic of PRS Hospital Trivandrum. The sample selected were 40 mothers of children aged less than 3 years who were using diaper for their child (at-least once in 24 hours) for the past 14 days and who were able to read and write Malayalam or English. Non-probability convenient sampling technique was used here.[19-24]

Tool used for data collection in the present study were.

Tool 1: Structured interview schedule to assess sociodemographic information.

Tool 2: Structured knowledge questionnaire

Tool 3: Reported practice checklist.

The content validity, the tool was evaluated by 4 experts including 3 pediatricians and 1 dermatologist. As per the suggestions of the experts, the tool was modified. Modifications were re-validated with the help of experts. The reliability of the tool was established by test-retest method.[25]

The ethical clearance was obtained from ethical committee. Formal permission was obtained from the Principal of PRS College of Nursing, Paliyode and Executive Medical Director of PRS Hospital, Trivandrum. To test the feasibility and practicability of the study, pilot study was conducted. The data was collected in 3 days. The investigator introduced herself to subjects and obtained informed consent from the participants by proper explanation of the study prior to data collection.[26,27]

The mothers were asked to complete the questionnaire for sociodemographic variables. After that, moms were given a checklist to evaluate their behaviors and a questionnaire to gauge their level of knowledge about managing and preventing diaper-related issues. WhatsApp numbers were collected by maintaining confidentiality. Maternal enlightenment programme was provided for mothers. The maternal enlightenment programme includes distribution of pamphlets, teaching with flashcards, power point presentation assisted teaching and video assisted learning. A teaching section was taken with help of pamphlets, flashcards and power point presentation and the video and power point presentation were sent to WhatsApp for reference and learning later. Later post-test were conducted on 7th day

after intervention by sending the questionnaire and checklist via WhatsApp.[28-30]

RESULTS

Section 1: Distribution of samples based on sociodemographic variables

- In the present study, (30%) of children belong to the age group of 6-12 months, (30%) belong to the 2-3 years, (25%) belongs to the age group of 1-2 years & (15%) belongs to age group <6 months.
- Majority, (65%) were males and (35%) were females.
- The present study reveals that, (80%) of the samples have one child, (20%) have 2 children and no one has 3 and 4 children.
- The feeding status shows that, (30%) has stopped breastfeeding and family feeding continuing, (25%) were breastfeeding along with family feeding, (23%) were on exclusive breastfeeding, (12%) has started weaning and breastfeeding continues and (10%) has started weaning and stopped breastfeeding.
- Majority, (45%) started weaning after 6 months, (35%) started at 6 months, (20%) were on exclusive breastfeeding and no one started weaning 6 months before.
- The allergic status reveals that (77.5%) have no allergy, (15%) have dust allergy and (7.5%) have food allergies.
- Among mothers, (55%) of mothers belong to age group 25-29 years, (22%) belong to 20-24 years, (15%) belongs to 30-34 years, (5%) belongs to 35-39 years and no one is <20 years and >39 years.
- In this study, (75%) belongs to nuclear family, (15%) belongs to joint family and (10%) belongs to extended family.
- The education status of mothers reveals that, (50%) of mothers are graduates, (27.5%) are postgraduates,

(12.5%) have higher secondary education, (5%) have diploma and (5%) have high school education.

- Among mothers, (55%) are working and (45%) are not working.
- In this study, (52.5%) of fathers are graduates, (15%) have diploma, (12.5%) have post-graduation, (10%) have high school education and (5%) have higher secondary education.
- Among the samples, (70%) uses disposable diapers, (30%) uses both types and no one uses cloth diapers only.
- The present study shows that, (60%) uses 1-2 diaper daily, (20%) uses 2-3 diapers, (15%) uses >5 diapers and (5%) uses 4-5 diapers.

Section 2: Knowledge and practice of the mothers regarding prevention and management of diaper related problems in pre and post test of maternal enlightenment programme

- In the knowledge pretest, the majority of samples (55%) had moderate knowledge, 40% had inadequate knowledge, and 5% had adequate knowledge.
- In posttest of knowledge, majority of samples having adequate knowledge (72.5%) and (27.5%) samples have moderate knowledge.
- In pretest of reported practice, majority of samples have fair level of practice (62.5%) and (30%) samples have poor level of practice and there was (7.5%) having good level of practice.
- In posttest of reported practice, majority of samples having good level of practice (82.5%) and (17.5%) samples have fair level of practice.

Section 3: Comparison between pre and post mean knowledge

- The mean value of pretest knowledge was 10.47 (SD=2.27) and posttest knowledge level is 17.12 (SD=2.24) and the mean difference (6.65), it indicates that the post mean value is greater than the mean value, & the t-value is (17.5).
- The mean value of pretest practice was 38.4 (SD=2.65) and posttest knowledge level is 45.82 (SD=2.28) and the mean difference (7.42), it indicates that the post mean value is greater than the mean value, & the t-value is (15.86).

Section 4: Association between the pretest level of knowledge and selected socio-demographic variables

- There was significant association between age of child and diaper related problems ($\chi^2=5.36$, $p=0.0206$).
- There was significant association between feeding status of child and diaper related problems ($\chi^2=6.45$, $p=0.0110$).
- There was significant association between weaning started age and diaper related problems ($\chi^2=3.57$, $p=0.0488$).
- There was significant association between education of mother of and diaper related problems ($\chi^2=10.55$, $p=0.0012$).
- There was significant association between education of father and diaper related problems ($\chi^2=10.87$, $p=0.0015$).
- There was significant association between number of diaper used and diaper related problems ($\chi^2=4.59$, $p=0.0478$).

It demonstrates that there was no significant correlation between the child's gender, number of children, allergy, mother's age, family type, mother's work, and diaper type.\

DISCUSSION

In the present study 65% of children were boys. In a study conducted to measure the knowledge of mothers about diaper rash and preventive measures in Bangladesh 55.45% of participated children were boys.

Out of 40 mothers who participated in the present study 55% of mothers were in the age group of 25-29 years. In a survey to assess knowledge of 100 mothers on diaper dermatitis conducted at Manguluru 38% were in the age group of 26-30 years.

In the present study 50% of mothers were graduates. A study to assess mother's knowledge and home management of nappy rash at Nigeria shown that 53.2% mothers participated had post-secondary education.

According to the present study 60% of mothers were doing 1-2 diaper changes per day for their child. A study to assess the knowledge and prevention of diaper rashes among mothers showed that 40.9% of mothers did 1-2 diaper changes per day.

In the present study the assessment of pretest knowledge regarding prevention and management of diaper related problems among mothers shows that 5% have adequate knowledge, Forty percent have insufficient knowledge, and fifty-five percent have moderate understanding. Additionally, the evaluation of pretest practice reveals that 7.5% have good practice, 62.5% have fair practice, and 30% have bad practice. According to the current study, mothers have a decent degree of practice and modest understanding when it comes to managing and preventing diaper-related issues. This was corroborated by a research done to evaluate the efficacy of a preventative awareness program and management of diaper dermatitis among mothers of children of age 0 to 1 year admitted in the Kasturba Hospital,

Manipal. It shows 54.8% had a moderate knowledge regarding prevention and management of diaper dermatitis.

In the present study the result showed that Maternal enlightenment program was effective in improving knowledge regarding prevention and management of diaper related problems. The mean knowledge score increased from 10.47 to 17.12. It is well supported by a study to assess the effectiveness of structured teaching program on knowledge and practice among mothers where the mean knowledge score increased from 13.92 to 19.

The present study results showed that mean practice score of mothers regarding prevention and management of diaper related problems increased from 38.4 to 45.82. A study that assessed the efficacy of an awareness program on the management and prevention of diaper dermatitis among mothers, which revealed an increase in mean practice score from 18.64 to 25.64 following the awareness program, corroborated these findings.

The study's data demonstrates a strong correlation between mothers' knowledge and practice ratings and the chosen sociodemographic factors such as age of child, gender of child, number of children, feeding status, weaning started, allergies, age of mother, type of family, education status of mother, occupation of mother, education status of father, type of diaper used, number of diapers per day.

LIMITATIONS

- The subjects had difficulty in attending direct teaching programme.
- The data collection period was short.
- Since post test was conducted via WhatsApp, only mothers who had smartphone and WhatsApp could be selected for the intervention.

The study findings revealed that there was a significant improvement in the knowledge and practice regarding prevention and management of diaper related problems after the Maternal enlightenment programme. The provision of Maternal enlightenment programme will improve the knowledge level of mothers and promote good practices. The improved knowledge and practice help in preventing the incidence of diaper related problems which contribute to health and quality of life of their children.

IMPLICATIONS

The findings of the study elicit the implication on nursing practice, nursing education, nursing administration and nursing research.

CONCLUSION

The study findings revealed that there was a significant improvement in the knowledge and practice regarding prevention and management of diaper related problems after the Maternal enlightenment programme. The provision of Maternal enlightenment programme will improve the knowledge level of mothers and promote good practices. The improved knowledge and practice help in preventing the incidence of diaper related problems which contribute to health and quality of life of their children.

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